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PTPRF has functions in pluripotency.

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Qualities of the stem cells of the embryo or the gametes include pluripotency and totipotency. Pluripotency as a quality that defines the embryonic stem cell is likely a process or entity distinguishable from the multi-lineage differentiation capacity that defines the HSC. We separated hematopoietic stem and embryonic stem programs for blind discovery of pluripotency-associated factors in the ES cell. We describe identification of PTPRF as a factor regulating or associated with pluripotency in human embryonic stem cells.

Citations

1. Liu, Z., Wang, P., Hu, Y., Zhang, N., Xu, L., Kang, T., Zhao, S., Zhao, D., Chan, C. and Li, J., 2026. Ptpf is the conserved receptor for Asprosin's glucogenic effects in vertebrates. Cell Reports, 45(2).